

Personal Health Goal

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Introduction

The health problem I need to target is my bad eating habits. I have concluded that I am guilty of four of the five most common bad eating habits. These habits include eating on the run, eating large portions, skipping meals, and late night eating. These habits are considered to be bad for various reasons. Eating on the run usually happens when a person is busy and does not have the time to cook a healthy meal. The result usually ends in fast and unhealthy meals as the food of choice. Eating on the run also causes a person to eat quickly usually causing one to eat larger portions in order for the hunger to be satisfied. When eating these unhealthy types of foods, especially in large portions, one tends to consume many more calories and much fewer nutrients (3FC, 2011).

Discussion

The second, third, and fourth bad habits, in my case, relate closely to one another. I have a busy schedule that keeps me on the go so I eat large portions when I have the opportunity to eat because I am unsure when I will have the chance to eat again. This is sometimes consistent with the next bad eating habit of skipping meals. This causes one to be hungrier at a later time which results in eating larger portions. I also work later into the evening. I get home and finish any projects that must be done by the night's end before I eat dinner. This is unhealthy since most people do lighter activities closer to their bed

time. This does not allow the body to burn the calories consumed and can cause unwanted weight gain (3FC, 2011).

In an effort to change these bad eating habits I am planning on using a few simple tips to help me to stay healthier from an eating viewpoint. The first tip I am going to use is to set myself up for success. This tip consists of three different pieces. First off, I will simplify my eating habits. In the beginning, I will not count calories but choose foods by color and freshness and incorporate them into my meals. The second piece is to make changes slowly (Paul, Smith, & Segal, 2011).

The second tip I will implement in my healthy eating plan is to remember that it is not just what I eat, but how I eat as well. This tip includes four ideas that can supplement my nutritional plan. The first idea is to eat with others when possible. When eating alone or while watching television, most people do not pay attention to what or how much they are eating. The second idea is to take the time to chew food and enjoy the meal. This allows you to slow down the eating process causing you to eat less. Idea three is to listen to your body. Sometimes you may think you are hungry when actually you could just need to rehydrate your body. A glass of water instead of a snack may be all that is needed. It is also better to stop eating before you feel full. Many times people will eat until this feeling occurs. Because it takes the brain a few minutes to realize that the stomach is full, you have already eaten more than you need. The final idea in this tip is to eat breakfast and smaller meals throughout the day. Eating breakfast starts the body's metabolism. When eating smaller meals throughout the day, the body's metabolism can continue at a normal rate. When waiting for long periods between eating, the metabolism

can slow down. Waiting until you are hungry to eat also results in eating larger portions during meals (Paul, Smith, & Segal, 2011).

To set this plan in motion, I am going to have to make better decisions when buying foods at the grocery store. I will need to make a list of the items that I intend to buy and make certain that

Conclusion

As I grow older I may need to make slight adjustments in my healthy eating plan in order to coincide with life's changes. Pregnancy could cause the need to change my cardio workout from running to walking. The workout would need to be less intense for safety purposes, yet still necessary for health reasons. It would also be imperative that I eat healthy to provide an adequate amount of vitamins, minerals, and nutrients for myself as well as the expected child. Adding prenatal vitamin supplements to my diet would help reach my nutrient goals (The Ohio State University, 2009). Age could also cause the need to change my physical workout because it could play a part in the ability to complete the regimen. I would still need to eat healthy foods, but I would also need to make certain that I drink plenty of water as not to dehydrate myself (Martinac, 2011). I believe that the healthy eating plan that I have created for myself is a feasible plan that could be implemented at any time within my life. It does not consist of a strict diet that would be difficult to follow. However, it will take willpower and desire to follow the tips that will help me lead a healthier lifestyle. The physical activities can always be molded to the changes that my life may bring. Whether it is changes in the seasons or changes within my body, working out in a gym gives me the ability to adapt to the needed changes.

References

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